

Materials solutions for cost Reduction and Extended service life on WIND off-shore facilities

MAREWIND is a research project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme. With a €6,7 million support from the EU, the project will provide vital solutions to help building a next generation of large offshore wind energy turbines.

HOW WILL THE PROJECT ACHIEVE THIS?

Its novel technologies will help solving the current challenges related to materials, coatings and architectural performance in the industry. With the combined forces of key-players in the current value chain of wind energy and offshore structures, MAREWIND covers a set of ambitious targets focused on:

- enhancing corrosion protection systems and durability;
- effective and durable antifouling solutions without using biocides;
- erosion protection and mechanical reinforcement of wind blades;
- predictive modelling and monitoring; and
- increasing recyclability.

MAKING A DIFFERENCE

MAREWIND is expected to strengthen the European leadership position in the industry and optimize the sector. Moreover, it will help reduce Europe's energy dependance and thereby delivers significant macroeconomic benefit:

- improving performance and durability of materials at optimized costs;
- significant reduction of life cycle costs;
- cost reduction for offshore energy production of about 40%;
- reducing of environmental impact by 35%, CO₂ emissions and fuel dependency;
- creating economic growth and jobs in Europe by strengthening the European industrial technology base.

STAY IN TOUCH

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